

Scalable production of solid-immersion lenses for quantum emitters in silicon carbide

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(Dated: 30 January 2020)

The 4H-silicon carbide (SiC) shows the capability to host a large number of promising emitters for quantum technology. However, due to its high refractive index, the collection of photoluminescence emission is compromised for further applications. Here, we demonstrate a scalable approach of manufacturing solid-immersion lenses (SILs) on 4H-silicon carbide (SiC). The fluorescence collection efficiency of single quantum emitters under the SILs shows 3.4 times enhancement confirmed by confocal microscopy of individual colour centers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide (SiC) is an appealing material for quantum technologies and nanophotonics due to its optical transparency, low nuclear spin bath¹ and mature SiC electronics². One species of promising quantum emitters found in the 4H-SiC polytype is the silicon vacancy defects V_{Si} ^{3,4}. It exhibits a long spin coherence time at room temperature and accessible coherence control of single spins⁵. However, the high refractive index of the material leads to strong refraction and total internal reflection at the SiC-air interface, which results in reduction of the collected defects photoluminescence. A possibility to circumvent this effect is the fabrication of shallow solid immersion lenses of a few micrometers in size on a SiC wafer, resulting in refractionless transmission of light through the SIL surface. A similar approach has already been proven to be advantageous for enhancing the fluorescence yield of nitrogen-vacancy (NV) centers in diamond^{6,7,8} or for studies in the spin properties of rare earth ions^{9,10}. Typically, SILs in diamond are fabricated by focused ion beam (FIB) milling¹¹. This approach is intrinsically time-consuming and unscalable. In addition, it leads to contamination of the surface of the SIL with gallium and damages the crystalline structure¹². Previous work on scalable photonics for SiC dealt with nanopillars tailored to 0.65 NA for signal collection, potentially with lensed fiber arrays¹³. With increasing NA of lensed fibers in experiments¹⁴ and theoretical proposals¹⁵, a high NA collection of light in a scalable fashion comes into reach.

Here, we introduce a scalable method of producing SILs capable to work with high NA objective by imprinting hemispherical droplets of a reflowed photoresist onto the surface of SiC by plasma etching. This is possible by etching SiC and organic polymers mask material with identical etching rates in a highly anisotropic plasma process. The performance of the resulting SILs is evaluated by comparing the fluorescence collected from single V_{Si} centers under the SIL with centers under a pristine SiC surface.

II. METHOD

The fabrication process consists of three consecutive steps¹⁶: photolithography, reflow process and plasma etching. A layer of $7\mu\text{m}$ negative photoresist material (AZ9260) is spin-coated on the SiC wafer and subsequently exposed by direct laser writing with a 405 nm diode laser to obtain photoresist pillars with different diameters, ranging from $4\mu\text{m}$ to $12\mu\text{m}$. The pillars are then subjected to a reflow process¹⁷ at 135°C in isopropanol atmosphere (see Fig. 1b). Due to the heating, the material softens and minimizes its surface energy taking a hemispherical shape. The result is shown as a AFM linescan of the hemispherical photoresist in Fig. 1d. The hemispherically shaped photoresist mask is then transferred into the SiC by reactive ion etching. The subsequent reactive ion etching step was conducted at $3\cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar pressure in an atmosphere containing HBr and Cl_2 in a commercially available RIE-ICP Plasma 100 Cobra system from Oxford Instruments¹⁸. The respective flow rates of HBr, which was 50.2 sccm, and Cl_2 , equal to 2.6, were set at a ratio of 1:20. The process was then run in a capacitively coupled plasma with a HF power being 101 W and a DC-bias of -411 V and in total absence of inductively coupled plasma (ICP). The two different gases employed in the process give different contribution during the etching process and their ratio related to the bias voltage was optimised in a few attempts. Most notably, with increasing HBr flow rate relative to Cl_2 flow rate, an increase in etch selectivity between photoresist and SiC was achieved. Plasma conditions with etching selectivity of 1:1 between photoresist and SiC were eventually chosen for mask transfer with an etch rate of ~ 40 nm per minute. The radius of curvature of several lenses with different diameters resulting from this process is investigated. As it can be seen from Fig. 1e and inset, the shape is not faithfully transferred to the wafer, nevertheless the apex of the lens has a spherical shape with an acceptance angle of 56° , confirming the functionality of a lens. At the end of the manufacturing process, an area of $600\mu\text{m} \times 600\mu\text{m}$ is covered with arrays of different lenses with diameter varied between $3\mu\text{m}$ and $10\mu\text{m}$, imaged by Secondary Electron Microscopy (SEM) as displayed in Fig. 1f.

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FIG. 1. Schematic of the fabrication process steps. (a) After spin-coating of a negative photoresist pillars are achieved through the use of photolithography. (b) Reflow process of pillars into hemispherical shape in isopropanol atmosphere at 135 °C (c) Reactive Ion Etching (RIE) transfers the profile into Si-C wafer. (d) Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) cross section linescans for one of the spheres after reflow process. (e) AFM cross section after RIE, inset zooms into the spherically shaped apex region of the SIL, that can be used to infer the NA of the top of the lens. (f) SEM image of the array of SILs and a zoom in one of the SILs produced.

FIG. 2. (a) Scanning confocal map of V_{Si} defects under the SIL in order to show the enhancement and functionality of the SIL. (b) Antibunching signal of a defect. Depicted antibunching measurements was taken on a colour center located in the apex region of the SIL. The signal amount to 0.15 at zero delay, indicative for a single photon source, i.e. a single V_{Si} center. (c) ODMR spectrum of a single V_{Si} with a characteristic resonance at 70 MHz which is equal to the zero-field splitting of V_2 .

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prior to lens fabrication, the n-doped SiC sample was irradiated with electrons of 2 MeV energy and a fluence of $10^{13}/cm^{-2}$ in order to create V_{Si} defect centers in the sample. The density of created V_{Si} allows for measurement of collection efficiency enhancement of fabricated lenses on the single defect center level. All optical measurements were done in a home-built confocal microscope setup, as shown in Ref⁵ (see supplementary material). A typical scanning confocal map of a SIL is shown in Fig. 2a, taken at half the total height of the SIL. Photon correlation measurements are used to confirm the single nature of the emitters. As an example, a typical normalized second order autocorrelation function of a V_{Si} under CW laser illumination located in the apex region a fabricated SIL is shown in Fig. 2b. The dip of the function at 0.15, well below 0.5 (dashed line) at zero delay, confirms the single photon source nature of the defect center. In order to confirm the species of emitters under studies, optically detected magnetic resonance (ODMR) is investigated for defects under the SILs. An ODMR spectrum of a single defect located under the SIL is taken. The measurement, shown in Fig. 2c, yields a peak at 70MHz, clearly identifying the V_2 vacancy center in SiC by the well-known zero-field-splitting^{5,19}(supplementary material for more information). When located outside the apex region, centers found in lenses show only moderate enhancement of the collection efficiency. But as expected from AFM linescans, defect centers residing in the spherically shaped apex region exhibit strongest enhancement and highest fluorescence emission. Since we created SILs with different diameters and heights, the enhancement of V_{Si} defects placed

FIG. 3. General quantum properties for V_{Si} in presence of solid immersion lens. (a) Statistics on different arrays of Sils manufactured in the process. The enhancement of defects placed at different height of Sils has a wide range up to 3.4. (b) Power-dependent fluorescence signal levels for the centers under the SIL and under the pristine SiC surface.

inside various SILs is investigated. A statistical study of the enhancement of these lenses has been conducted and is shown in Fig. 3a. For the presented data, 49 lenses of different sizes were investigated with respect to their enhancement of single V_{Si} emitters. Considering a normal distribution of enhancements, the analysis shows an average enhancement of 2.1 with a standard deviation of 0.6. Moreover, no correlation between size of the lens and its enhancement was found. We conjecture, that due to the relatively low density of V_{Si} , the positioning of the individual V_{Si} with respect to the apex region is the dominating influence on emission enhancement. Collection efficiency enhancement was quantified in a laser power dependent fluorescence intensity measurement on V_{Si} defects located both, in the pristine SiC and in the apex region. After a background subtraction similar to Ref²⁰, we find the fluorescence signal for both cases, as shown in Fig. 3b. Intensity curves are fitted to $I(P) = \frac{I_{sat} \cdot P}{(P + P_{sat})}$, where I_{sat} is the saturated fluorescence intensity and P_{sat} represents the saturating power of the laser²¹. The black-square curve describes the fluorescence of one defect present in the apex region of the SIL with a saturation fluorescence $I_{sat}^{SIL} = (37.90 \pm 0.38) \cdot 10^3$ counts per second(cps). The blue-dotted curve represents fluorescence of a defect in the pristine region and in absence of the SIL with a saturation fluorescence $I_{sat}^{NoSIL} = (11.65 \pm 0.09) \cdot 10^3$ cps. According to these results, the presence of SIL results in an

enhancement $\frac{I_{sat}^{SIL}}{I_{sat}^{NoSIL}} = 3.4$. An important figure of merit is the signal-to-background, e.g. when discussing investigation of spin properties of single colour centers. The enhancement of signal-to-background ratio amounts to 2.2 for the two defects of Fig. 3b.

CONCLUSION

Based on high selectivity of reactive ion etching of SiC with respect to photoresist, we developed a scalable method of manufacturing SILs. With this procedure it is possible to create a wide range of SILs with an average fluorescence enhancement of more than 2 that show suitable feature for long-time measurements. In the best manufactured SIL, according to the comparison between the photoluminescence emitted by a color center in the hemispherical region of the lens and one residing in the pristine region, an enhancement of 3.4 is achieved. Moreover, SILs manufactured with this procedure can be readily used for low temperature measurements of defects in SiC^{22,23}.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author wants to acknowledge Kangwei Xia for his help and suggestions in the writing of the manuscript.

RK acknowledges financial support by DFG (Grant No. KO4999/3-1). RK and JW acknowledge financial support by the EU via SMEL and QIA as well as the DFG via FOR 2724. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820391(SQUARE).

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